

Reviewer 3

The paper has a very high quality of figures and presentations. The topic is interesting, but it is hard to follow how each component in the document is helping the major purpose of the paper. I understand that they are trying to investigate the improved forecasting skill when adding a new LULC dataset. And you present a very provocative clue about the urban heat of 6C. However, a lot of the description in the paper does not seem to fix well. For example, this paragraph:

We appreciate all your comments. After a careful revision of the manuscript that considered your comments and those from others anonymous reviewers, we consider that this version has greatly improved. Listed below is a description of the major modifications we made to the manuscript.

- The final part of the “Abstract” has been modified in order to clarify some points mentioned by the reviewers.
- In the section “1. Introduction”, we have modified two paragraphs and defined the objective in a scientific way and more explicitly. We have also added a paragraph that describes the content of the article.
- We have reorganized and added subsections in section “3. Methods and data”:
 - 3.1. Model configuration
 - 3.2. Description and assessment of the experiments
 - 3.3. Observational data
 - 3.4. LULC dataset
 - 3.4.1 Changes of LULC
- A subsection on section “4. Results and discussion” was added to discuss the physical processes involved.
- Section “5. Conclusions” was modified at the suggestion of removing some sentences.
- The citation of some references was revised and modified.
- LULC's change matrix was added in supplemental material.
- We have checked the manuscript for errors in English language and style.

In the following we reply to comments and suggestions step by step.

Note: Line numbers refer to the original manuscript.

Ln 21

“The LSM used in the operational weather forecast is based on the MM5 5-layer soil temperature scheme [26, 27]. Without including explicit vegetation effects, this scheme employs the thermal diffusion equation and the force-restore method to calculate soil temperatures [28, 46, 47] with fixed soil- layer thicknesses of 1, 2, 4, 8 and 16 cm. Below the bottom level, at 31 cm, the substrate temperature is kept constant in a layer that is 32 cm thick. The energy budget includes radiation, and sensible and latent heat flux. Soil moisture is fixed with a land cover and season dependent constant value. Table 4 presents the physical properties of the terrain associated with each land cover used by the 5-layer scheme. Each land cover type (vegetation, urban, water, etc.) is assigned with a summer/winter value for albedo, emissivity and surface roughness length.”

It sounds that this section is just filling a gap. Information is good but it has to play a role. This paragraph will lose readers as it did with me.

Response: We appreciate the comment. We have modified this paragraph and we have only left the important information that helps to present the parameters associated with each type of cover land.

A Similar situation occurs before in Page 5 Ln21-31 “It is noteworthy ...”

This is not bad information, but you have to decide what is the central topic of the paper. If the new dataset is the central topic, this should be appropriated, but if the topic is forecast quality, you should add the detail of what this means in the context of LULC: forecasting skill.

Response: Thanks for the observation, we have rephrased the sentences from line 21-31 in Page 5. We have added the detail of what this means in the context of LULC and in the forecasting skill.

Mention how you compute forecasting skill in the method as to why two experiments are enough, and if not, you present some caveats of the study. So, readers are aware.

Response: Thanks for the observation. We have added a new subsection “3.2. Description and evaluation of the experiments” where we describe the points indicated above. In the revised manuscript you could find it.

In the abstract, you mention wind and temperature, so I was expecting to see that in the methodology and the rest of the discussion, as you did in the conclusion.

Response: Thanks for the observation. We have reorganized section “3. Methods and data” and in the discussion we have added key points in each variable in order to better describe our results (subsection 4.4). We hope that the revised version of the manuscript helps in clarifying this point.

My apologies I do not bring good news on your paper but working more time on this one that has a lot of good points. For example, the new dataset, the WRF experiments, the sites with local information about the land.

Response: We appreciate the careful reading and comments provided by the referee, which helped in improving this manuscript. We hope that the revised version helps in clarifying all points mentioned above.